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Research Article

Blockchain-based secure dining: Enhancing safety, transparency, and traceability in food consumption environment

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ABSTRACT

This research paper seeks to examine the possibilities of blockchain technology. For use in the field of restaurant food tracking and safety. Public health risks and economic costs are at stake when foodborne illness outbreaks occur, making food safety a top priority in the food industry. It can be difficult to quickly identify and address possible concerns about using traditional food traceability systems due to inefficiencies, data discrepancies, and a lack of transparency. In this study, we introduce a novel blockchain-based system developed especially for the purpose of tracking restaurant food. Blockchain decentralised consensus, immutability, and smart contracts are put to use in this system to provide trustworthy and transparent traceable infrastructure. Real-time monitoring and data collection along the food supply chain become possible when the blockchain architecture is combined with the Internet of Things (IoT) devices and RFID technology. We show that our proposed blockchain-based traceability solution is practical and efficient through a thorough assessment and validation procedure. The outcomes show that the system not only improves data quality and reliability but also drastically decreases the time and resources needed for food traceability. In addition, patrons are more likely to return to eateries that place a premium on food safety when they are given more information about the establishment's practises. Additionally, we discuss scalability, data privacy, and interoperability concerns that may arise in future implementations and provide some initial ideas for overcoming these issues.

1. Introduction

The restaurant industry has undergone significant and noteworthy expansion in recent years, mostly driven by the increasing global demand for diverse foreign cuisines and distinctive dining experiences [1]. However, issues of food safety, quality, and traceability have been brought to light as a result of this explosive growth. In order to solve these problems and regain consumers' trust, new technologies have been investigated [2,3]. There are many potential solutions, but blockchain technology stands out as particularly effective because of the extraordinary transparency and efficiency it provides in food tracking.

Blockchain was developed first for powering digital currencies; it is a distributed, immutable digital ledger that can be used to record any kind of transaction or piece of data in a completely transparent and auditable way [4]. It runs on a decentralised network of computers in which each participant (node) keeps a copy of the whole ledger, which prevents tampering with the data without the agreement of the network as a whole. Due to its distinctive design, blockchain holds great potential for improving food supply chain transparency in the hospitality industry.

Implementing blockchain technology in the context of food security can potentially reduce time and resource requirements in various ways, such as improving traceability, where blockchain enables transparent and immutable tracking of the entire supply chain. If a food safety issue arises, identifying the source becomes significantly faster, reducing the time needed for investigations. This quick traceability can prevent widespread outbreaks and reduce the resources required to manage such crises. Blockchain can optimize inventory management by providing real-time data on the movement of goods in the supply chain. This real-time visibility helps prevent overstocking or understocking of products, reduce waste, and optimize the allocation of resources.

In this article, we explore in greater detail the possibilities of using blockchain technology to track and guarantee the safety of food served in restaurants. We investigate how issues including food poisoning, contamination, incorrect labelling, and supply chain inefficiencies have damaged public faith in the food industry and cost businesses and individuals dearly.

Additionally, we examine how the immutable and transparent nature of blockchain technology might revolutionise the food supply chain by

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granting instantaneous access to critical data, including the source of ingredients, production methods, transit information, and storage environments. Blockchain's cryptographic algorithms and smart contracts enable producers, suppliers, restaurants, regulatory authorities, and customers to work together effectively, expedite processes, and guarantee compliance with food safety norms and laws.

Throughout this paper, we highlight real-world applications of blockchain technology in the restaurant sector. We look at how improved traceability helps in areas such as detecting and stopping food poisoning outbreaks quickly, cutting down on food waste, enhancing inventory management, and boosting customer confidence by providing them with access to trustworthy data about products.

However, we are also aware of the difficulties and potential restrictions that may arise from using blockchain for tracking food. Some of these include uncertainty about how well the system can scale, compatibility problems with other systems, high setup costs, and reluctance to abandon tried and true methods. We discuss how these challenges may be surmounted and offer suggestions for moving forward with blockchain technology in the hospitality industry.

Finally, this article argues that restaurants should utilise blockchain technology as a game-changing approach for improving food traceability and guaranteeing food safety. By using the blockchain's inherent qualities of transparency, immutability, and decentralisation, stakeholders may collaborate to construct a food supply chain that is more secure, reliable, and trustworthy. Because of rising customer expectations for safe, sustainable, and traceable food supplies, the implementation of blockchain technology represents a significant step towards transforming the future of the restaurant industry and reimagining the way we eat.

The manuscript is organised as follows: Section 1 further describes the motivation and contribution of the proposed work, followed by challenges in the existing system and the introduction of blockchain technology. In Section 2, relevant research is presented, including a comparison of current supply chain management practises and blockchain use cases. The methodology is discussed in detail in Section 3. The specifics of the plan's execution may be found in Section 4. Section 5 displays the results and discusses the findings. Section 6 provides a contrast to the current system. Section 7 discusses the challenges and potential solutions. Section 8 explains the implications of the work, and Section 9 provides the conclusion and suggestions for further research.

1.1. Motivation

The planned effort is meant to address the critical issue of food safety in the hospitality industry. This research aims to use blockchain technology to create a trustworthy and secure food tracking system that can monitor distribution from farm to fork. The goal of this strategy is to promote public health and safety by providing customers access to reliable information about the source, preparation, and safety of the food they purchase.

1.2. Contribution

The widespread adoption of blockchain technology has the ability to transform food safety procedures and industry norms, making for a more secure and reliable food ecosystem for all participants. This study presents a realistic and comprehensive framework for improving restaurant food traceability and safety and contributes to the expanding body of knowledge on blockchain applications.

1.3. Existing food supply chain system: challenges

When substantial amounts of tainted items have been sold across vast markets, traceability becomes extremely important in the case of a recall to safeguard consumer health. Manufacturers and suppliers can benefit from traceability for supply chain management and customer

satisfaction [5]. The ability to track the journey of a product from a farm through the food processing industry, the retail and food service sectors, and finally into the house is becoming increasingly important [6]. An increase in income means that people are increasingly aware of the safety, freshness, and provenance of the food they eat. Because of this, businesses are under pressure to adopt cutting-edge technology to provide their consumers with the highest possible value. As consumers become more aware of food safety issues, there is a growing demand for accurate and trustworthy data presented in an approachable fashion [7]. There were a number of distressing incidents in the 1990s that brought attention to food safety, including an outbreak of bovine spongiform encephalopathy in the United Kingdom, dioxin contamination of chicken feed in Belgium, and melamine contamination in China [8].

It is well established that inappropriate food storage and handling pose threats to public health. Approximately 48 million Americans fall victim to a foodborne illness each year, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). According to the WHO, tainted food causes illness in one in ten people and the deaths of 420,000 people annually. Significant and long-lasting economic damage was done to spinach growers due to an inability to quickly detect and determine the source of the tainted spinach, and as a result, customer trust was eroded. Both a large pork mislabelling scandal and contamination fraud involving donkey meat products that were falsely said to include fox meat rocked in China in 2011. Melamine, Sudan red, clenbuterol, Sanlu hazardous milk powder, and trench oil were the other pollutants that made their way into the food supply in China, further undermining consumer confidence in the food industry. The Chinese agri-food loss ratio is between 25% and 30% yearly due to the country's complicated and antiquated agricultural food logistics networks. The Office of Economic Cooperation and Development has identified several challenges within the food value chain, including information deficiencies at various levels, decentralised food storage, food waste in the restaurant and catering sectors, and inadequate coordination between regulatory agencies and ministries. In 2013, there was an occurrence inside the European Union supply chain when individuals involved in criminal activities replaced lamb and beef with horsemeat. At least one thousand tonnes of food, or more than four and a half million processed goods, were harmed by illicit replacement. Profits and company credibility were irreparably harmed by this scam. Food theft costs the food business across the world an estimated \$40 billion annually, as reported by Price Waterhouse Coopers and Safe and Secure Approaches in Field Environments. A widespread *Salmonella* epidemic in the United States in July 2017 was traced back to papayas sold on the market. The CDC recorded 173 cases of salmonellosis, 58 cases of hospitalisation, and one case of death by mid-August 2017. After health officials issued a warning, consumers and businesses were urged to stop selling and consuming papayas. It took almost three weeks for health officials to track the cause of the illness down to a single farm in Mexico, even after they replicated the procedures they had taken during the spinach incident. The inability to swiftly identify and trace food goods has caused economic losses for papaya producers in unaffected areas [9].

In order to ensure the long-term viability of the food supply chain, it is important for businesses to address the concerns of their stakeholders regarding the availability of reliable information [10]. Customers have an inherent and fundamental right to eat safely. Foodborne diseases remain a major public health problem worldwide, despite numerous advances in food science and safety. In the United States alone, the CDC estimates that more than 48 million individuals each year lose their lives as a result of eating tainted food. As a result, 128,000 people are admitted to hospitals, and 3000 lose their lives [11].

Maintaining a healthy population is essential for many other goals, including economic growth and long-term viability. Since the production and consumption of safe and standard food in a particular community are euphemisms for that community's public health, the public health of that community may be understood on the boundaries of the current food chain in that community. The commercialization of the

food business, expansions in the international trade market for food supplies, and developments in food production and consumption technology all point towards a brighter economic future. However, the professional attitudes of manufacturers, producers, dealers, suppliers, and consumers alike in relation to health concerns, legal rights, and logistical benefits have been a boon to the food sector as a whole. The quick influx of other cuisines, improved transportation, and exciting new culinary experiments have raised the risk for both the food industry and its consumers. The Maggie debate demonstrated the public's heightened sensitivity to health issues. The media is always interested in stories about food contamination, food product adulteration, etc. Because studies on food safety and standards are uncommon in India, especially from a legal perspective, rising public anxiety over this topic inspired us to conduct this study. The stated traceability system may be used for any food safety issues, such as quality, adulteration, waste, and demands for regulation and standards. Increased customer expectations worldwide for traceability, nutritional value, safety, and quality increase the complexity of the food supply chain. The supply chain itself raises a number of issues of concern in terms of food quality and safety. In order to solve these issues permanently, businesses are looking for systems that are both effective and scalable.

Trust transfer occurs between two adjacent nodes [12]. The issue of trust transfer is a prevalent challenge within contemporary traceability systems. This matter is elucidated by the inclusion of Fig. 1, which depicts a supply chain specifically designed for a restaurant setting. The supply chain consists of four nodes: A (Distributor), B (Retailer), C (Restaurant), and D (Customer). In this supply chain, trust pairs (A, B), (B, C), and (C, D) exist.

Now, sometimes the trust pair (C, D) wants to communicate and share data. For example, the customer (D) requests information about the ingredients from the restaurant (C), but the restaurant cannot provide the requested information because it is not authorised. Although both nodes are part of a trust pair, they cannot fulfil the request due to limitations in conventional supply chains.

Let us consider another example. Suppose restaurant node (C) acts as a retailer and sends a request to node A, the distributor, asking for source data. In response, the distributor (A) declines the request because it does not have any information from node C. The challenge of resolving indirect trade interactions by means of interaction and iterative collaboration to ascertain their accuracy poses a significant strain on the entire system.

1.4. The blockchain technology

Blockchain is a cutting-edge innovation that functions as a decentralised digital ledger that can track transactions over many blocks. Because no single party is responsible for maintaining security in this system, it is inherently safe. Public blockchains, private blockchains, and hybrid blockchains are the three most common types of blockchains. Similarities between public and private blockchains include immutability, distributed nature, and reliance on consensus processes and encryption for security. The consensus procedure and ongoing upkeep of the distributed ledger are different for public and private blockchains [10,13–18]. The Bitcoin blockchain serves as a prominent illustration of a public blockchain that enables global accessibility for anyone to both access and contribute information. Only verified and authorised users can access the data on a private blockchain. The advantages of both a private, permissioned blockchain and a public, untraceable blockchain are combined in a hybrid blockchain. This implementation model provides business partners with the freedom to decide what information to share publicly and what to keep confidential. A block is a unit of data that includes both a header and a set of transactions. The creation time of the block, the hash of the preceding block, the hash of the current block, and the Merkle root are all included in the block header. The current block's hash is calculated by taking the Merkle root of the transactions and the hash of the previous block [19]. This means that

chronologically ordered blocks are linked together by appending each subsequent block to the one that came before it. The genesis block, or block₁, is used as a key in the computation of the hash of the subsequent block, as shown in Fig. 2. Similarly, block₂ hash is used as a parameter in block₃. Because of this setup, exchanges cannot be tampered with Ref. [20]. For the many parties engaged in the value chain, including farmers, distributors, retailers, and consumers, blockchain represents a fresh ray of hope for quality control systems. The primary goal of this study is to create a workable prototype of a blockchain-based system that can be used by eateries to comply with government regulations and improve the quality of the food they provide to customers. When used to trace the quality of food, blockchain guarantees standardisation, cost-effectiveness, information safety, and dependability [21].

2. Related work

There is a growing need for food traceability in order for businesses to gain an edge in the market and effectively handle issues of food safety and nutrition. Consumers now have greater standards for not only taste but also for hygiene and originality in their food as a result of rising incomes. For this purpose, George et al.'s proof-of-concept prototype collects information from participants in the food supply chain, organises it, and then runs it through the Food Quality Index (FQI) algorithm to derive an FQI score [7]. Lin et al. [12] proposed a management architecture for on-chain and off-chain data through which a traceability method can reduce the blockchain's data explosion concern for the IoT blockchain has several uses outside of cryptocurrencies because of its ability to guarantee transactional privacy, authenticity, integrity, and non-repudiation. A medical data-sharing scheme was proposed by Pandey and Litoriya [20]. The resulting system is computationally demanding but provides a data provenance solution to the problem of counterfeit drugs. dos Santos et al. [21] analysed the traceability needs of recipe-based foods and suggested an alternative method to full chain traceability through ingredient certification. In the field of digital rights management, Pănescu and Manta [22] used blockchain technology and smart contracts to introduce a new approach to regulating the digital reuse rights of research data. Patki and Sople [23] highlighted how blockchain technology is tackling critical concerns such as data transmission speed and security from multiple transaction partners, payment processing costs, and services in the banking sector. In the area of health sector blockchain, the biggest milestone authors [18,24–26] proposed a solution for the healthcare system by implementing the AarogyaChain decentralised architecture for securing records and providing authenticity and privacy. Lone and Naaz [27] emphasised the enhanced security brought about by smart contracts in the realms of the Internet and IoT. Additionally, they addressed the existing constraints that hinder the widespread use of blockchain smart contracts for security purposes. Kashyap and Saurav [28] investigated the weaknesses of the present procedures and governance structure and provided insight into how blockchain can restructure governance in Indian banks. Muminova et al. [29] provided information about Uzbekistan should adopt the practise of employing blockchain technologies to accelerate the digitalisation of the national economy. Leduc et al. [30] proposed a novel blockchain-based farming marketplace platform called "FarMarketplace" for proper channels between farmers and third-party stakeholders to prevent the privileges of farmers. In addition, Rohmah et al. [31] and Tan et al. [32] introduced blockchain technology as a conceptual framework for blockchain-based halal food monitoring and traceability and investigated its potential effects on the food industry's capacity to compete. Table 1 presents some blockchain applications in various fields and their analysis, and Table 2 presents blockchain applications in the food traceability field.

The aforementioned use cases collectively demonstrate the significance of food traceability. Based on an extensive literature review, it is evident that the present food service providers are unable to sufficiently cater to the demand for meals, kitchens, and the local market. Because

Fig. 1. Traditional supply chain for restaurants with a trust transfer problem.

there are currently no rules or regulations governing how meals are supplied, many providers must be consulted as part of the quality assurance process. Having multiple restaurants operate under one authority does not constitute automation in the food-providing industry. The restaurant should be in charge of all aspects of the food service, from providing the ingredients to providing timely, high-quality delivery of the meals to the customers [37].

To ensure the purity and quality of food, there should be some trustworthy solutions based on cutting-edge technology so that the end user can benefit and receive the promised food and services.

3. Methodology

This investigation takes into account the voids identified in the literature and the evidence presented in scholarly works. Many models already in use that make use of technology have been studied.

In order to create a unique methodology for tracing the quality of food and communicating that information to all parties involved in the

supply chain. To establish a standard by which to evaluate the quality of food served at eateries, a comprehensive search was conducted. The following approach is explained with the help of a typical Indian eatery in the area. When new issues arose, we spoke with several hotel management companies for advice. A comparison was performed so that we could better understand the ease of use of the technologies, the authenticity of the information, the avoidance of manipulation, and the various hazards associated with data management. It has been concluded that the blockchain paradigm offers superior scalability, reliability, and overall cost-effectiveness.

In the first phase, the supplier purchases groceries directly from the farmer, establishing a relationship based on trust and honesty. After that, the manufacturer ships the food supplies to the local wholesaler or retailer. The consumer’s needs are met when the retailer or distributor hands off all necessary materials to the restaurant. For each individual item of merchandise, each sub-package, and each wholesale order, a unique QR code must be used to participate in the proposed system.

Material details, supplier name and license, production date,

Fig. 2. Structure of blocks in blockchain.

Table 1
Blockchain applications in various fields and their analysis.

Use cases	Area	Objective	Key contribution	Result	1	2	3	4	5
Pandey and Litoriya [20]	Medicine sector	Combat the spread of fake pharmaceuticals in India.	Keeping track of what has to be done, from drug production to patient.	Method for people to check the legitimacy of the drugs they take.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pănescu and Manta [22]	Intellectual Property Right (IPR)	Research data re-use management system for digital archives.	Accords were reached between data creators and users.	Using the Solidity smart contract framework to implement a workflow.	✓	✓	✓	x	✓
Patki and Sople [23]	Banking sector	Problems like slow or insecure data transfer in the banking system need to be fixed.	Eliminate the requirement for several parties to verify the annual validity of transactions by automating the verification process.	Transactional security, trustworthiness, and decentralisation.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pandey and Litoriya [26]	Health sector	Difficulties in establishing comprehensive healthcare services on a broad scale, from a social and technological perspective.	Suggested methods for smoothing out the health policy rollout.	By developing a blockchain and determining the system throughput, we have successfully implemented.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pandey and Litoriya [18]	Health sector	Prevent the negative effects of centralization on the healthcare system.	A distributed e-healthcare information network is proposed.	Safe blockchain-based design adapted to the demands of e-health infrastructure.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Lone and Naaz [27]	Internet and the Internet of Things (IoT)	A detailed analysis of how smart contracts may be used to protect the IoT and the Internet.	Find and evaluate research that has explored the application of blockchain smart contracts for Internet security.	This analysis sheds light on the challenges and possible areas for future study in using blockchain smart contracts for enhancing security in the context of the Internet and IoT.	-	-	-	-	-
Kashyap and Saurav [28]	Banking sector	In order to analyse how India's government can function more effectively.	Take a look at the current systems and the problems with the way things are run.	Governance in Indian banks may be reorganised with the use of blockchain technology.	✓	✓	✓	✓	x
Muminova et al. [29]	National economy	Analysis of the elements of the emerging digital economy.	Make a case for using blockchain at the national level.	Ways to construct and grow significant financial initiatives at the state level in Uzbekistan and to apply the digital economy.	✓	✓	✓	✓	x
Leduc et al. [30]	ICT	ICT-enabled agricultural innovation.	Tracking and tracing food is a primary emphasis of blockchain-based agricultural systems.	New decentralised marketplace for farmers (dubbed "FarMarketplace").	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

1. Privacy 2. Trust 3. Security 4. Scalability 5. Lake of intermediaries [33].

expiration date, batch number, total amount produced in this batch, and authorised logistic partner information are all included in the QR code. The suggested system relies heavily on QR coding, which eliminates the possibility of tainted goods entering the supply chain [18].

Fig. 3 depicts the workflow that was used to create the suggested system using a blockchain. A stepwise approach is described to discourage the development and market penetration of adulterated food material:

Table 2
Blockchain applications in the food traceability field.

Authors	Year	Objective	Key contribution	Result
George et al. [7]	2019	Significant existing food traceability technologies are analysed.	Provides a prototype for utilising blockchain and product IDs to provide more dependable food tracking in dining establishments.	Applying the Food Quality Index (FQI) method, we may determine whether or not a certain food item is fit for human consumption.
Lin et al. [12]	2019	The individual's decision-making process was impacted by the prevailing circumstances surrounding the food safety issue. The establishment of a robust traceability system is of utmost importance.	This study aims to develop a proof-of-concept system that utilises blockchain technology and the EPCIS for the purpose of tracing the origin of food.	An Ethereum-based prototype system has been built.
dos Santos et al. [21]	2019	In order to provide a system for certifying the reliability of ingredients used by consumers.	Without hurting the food processor, guarantee the client knows where each item came from in the recipe.	The IGR Ethereum token has been implemented.
Rohmah et al. [31]	2019	Researching halal food tracking and traceability systems.	This document encompasses a proposition for the establishment of a halal food supply chain, together with a conceptual framework for a monitoring and traceability system specifically designed for halal food.	The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) technology is proposed to enhance the monitoring and tracking of all stakeholders involved in the supply chain during the execution of halal food certification.
Yu et al. [34]	2020	A smart system for tracking fruit juice-making processes.	Models of the system's response surface are built using information gathered before production begins, and the conditions under which those stages yield the best results are determined.	The juice manufacturing system is built on the Ethereum platform and is run in the Remix integrated development environment.
Radain et al. [35]	2021	The Hajj season: A case study in automating food production services.	Automating the entire process of supplying meals is one approach you may propose.	The blockchain-enabled Bizagi platform is the basis for the proposed simulation.
Cocco et al. [36]	2021	Managing the supply chain for a certain type of Italian bread.	Carasau bread's supply chain is transparent and auditable, allowing all participants to check the product's quality.	Nodes with built-in sensors are directly linked to Raspberry Pi devices in a system established in tandem with the supply chain.

Fig. 3. Proposed system based on blockchain.

Fig. 4. Hyperledger architecture for restaurant blockchain.

1) Assume a licensed distributor ships 100 packages of food products in one go. Each individual product (carton) will have the same batch number if it comes from the same production run. Nonetheless, a specific number assigned to each unit (carton) allows for easy

identification. A distributed ledger called a blockchain stores all of this information.

2) The same 100 units (cartons) created are shipped by the same supplier unit to the registered logistics partner. At this point, the logistics partner will check the authenticity of the unit (carton) and will only

Fig. 5. Flowchart for the internal working of the hyperledger fabric-based architecture.

- accept the shipment if it is legitimate. This transfer will be recorded in the blockchain database. The same procedure for updating the ledger will be carried out at each handoff if the logistics system is expanded to include additional logistic partners. In this step, we check to see that our consignment flow is uniform across the board.
- 3) Third, once the validity of the cargo has been confirmed, the logistics partners will deliver the food item material to the local distributor/retailer. At this time, it is important to remember that local distributors and retailers will receive varying numbers of consignments. Each transfer will automatically refresh the ledger. In this step, we check that the right amount of authentic food material is distributed throughout the supply chain.
 - 4) The wholesaler or retailer in the area delivers the goods to the restaurant, which then splits them among the various sections (inventory, kitchen, etc.) as requested. The blockchain-based ledger records all of these transfers as well.

- 5) At the culmination of the hierarchical structure, the customer will inquire about the quality and amount of the food items and verify their legitimacy by scanning a QR code printed on the bill. If the customer believes that the cuisine is not real, he or she will not pay the cost. After a customer dines at the restaurant and pays the tab, the appropriate entries are made in the ledger. At this stage in the life cycle of the food supply chain, the restaurant’s sales have closed the loop [18].

4. Implementation

Fig. 4 shows a simulation of the proposed system, which is founded on the Hyperledger Fabric framework and executed on a local network employing fifteen personal computers operating on the Windows 64-bit platform. The system under consideration is founded on a permissioned blockchain. Within the simulated network, a certain PC is assigned the role of a consumer, which may encompass several devices, such as

```

CXX(target) Release/obj.target/pkcs11/src/pkcs11/param_ecdh.o
CXX(target) Release/obj.target/pkcs11/src/pkcs11/pkcs11.o
CXX(target) Release/obj.target/pkcs11/src/async.o
CXX(target) Release/obj.target/pkcs11/src/node.o
SOLINK_MODULE(target) Release/obj.target/pkcs11.node
COPY Release/pkcs11.node
make: Leaving directory '/home/ubuntu/fabric-samples/fabcar/node_modules/pkcs11js/build'
npm notice created a lockfile as package-lock.json. You should commit this file.
npm WARN ajv-keywords@2.1.1 requires a peer of ajv@^5.0.0 but none was installed.
npm WARN fabcar@1.0.0 No repository field.

+ grpc@1.18.0
+ fabric-ca-client@1.3.0
+ fabric-client@1.3.0
added 743 packages in 44.441s
    
```

Fig. 6. Screenshot of installing a fabric client.

(Fig. 8).

The viability of the RW sets in light of the existing network state is also evaluated. Even if the transaction is registered on the ledger, the real network state will not be altered if the RW settings are no longer valid. If this is a successful transaction, the customer application (Supplier 'X') will be informed. Similarly, at various handoff points, several customers would ask the network to provide the necessary services.

5. Results and discussion

The throughput of the implemented system is determined by testing it in a variety of environments. The success of a run is measured by how many blocks it produces within a certain time constraint (Table 3). Fig. 9 shows the throughput performance of the system. Fig. 9 shows that there is no consistent pattern in how system performance changes between configurations. However, the throughput is shown to be significantly affected by the number of ordering nodes. Fig. 10 shows that the throughput of a system is positively correlated with the number of ordering nodes. The same number of nodes can either endorse or commit at different rates (Figs. 11 and 12).

Therefore, it is reasonable to infer that system performance (in terms of throughput) is proportional to the number of ordering nodes and that committing and endorsing nodes have an additive impact. Fewer ordering or committing nodes provide less of a threat to the system's security, but they also have less of an impact on the system's performance.

The proposed system is designed to be resilient against different types of attacks. Here is a description of how it ensures safety.

Scenario 1: Suppose that distributor A transfers 12 units (cartons) of material to a retailer through logistics, with each unit having an identification mark indicating its batch number, such as batch A1. However, before reaching the retailer, let us say that some units, specifically five units, are stolen. These stolen units are then sold on the retail market at a lower price.

Handling: The units (cartons) have batch numbers specified on them from the beginning, as described in the methodology, such as batches A1U1 to A1U12. Additionally, each sub-packet within the units has a unique QR code. Now, if the logistics deliver fewer units, let us say 5 units (cartons), to the retailer, this discrepancy is immediately noticed. The retailer can promptly report this to the division of food safety for investigation.

Scenario 2: Suppose the food inspection officer frequently visits the restaurant to test the food and audit the inventory of the restaurant.

Handling: If the amount of material that has come from the retailer to the restaurant matches the amount that the restaurant owner has purchased and used, then the usage of material will be equal to the consumption of material. This ensures that the food quality and taste, as per their standards, are maintained. However, if there is a discrepancy between the inventory and the actual usage in the restaurant, the material has been handled in an unauthorised manner, and appropriate actions will be taken to address the matter separately.

Scenario 3: If any unit (carton) in the supply chain has been tampered with during a handover or if adulteration has occurred in any material at the restaurant and if the remaining items are sold on the market, it would be considered a breach of quality control and food safety standards.

Handling: In the supply chain, customers never purchase any item that does not provide proof of its authenticity through a QR code. Customers rely on QR codes to ensure the genuineness and authenticity of the products they purchase.

6. Comparison with existing systems

Table 4 shows a review of alternative systems to the proposed system. The four systems compared are traditional systems, which are still utilised in the majority of restaurant supply chain systems in India. All

handovers are documented on this system. Publications and each participant must rely on others in the network. It is quite difficult to trace the origin of foodstuff material or any other disagreement.

The solution proposed by some authors, such as dos Santos et al. [21], solves the problems of ingredient certification and quality checking of ingredients. However, this technology is limited to a specific geographical area and does not provide a completely trustworthy computing environment. Second, Radain et al. [35] provided a better understanding of ingredient quality checking, but the main disadvantage of this method is that it has a single point of failure. Finally, yet importantly, Cocco et al. [36] provided a solution against the single point of failure and ingredient certification, but this solution is not suitable for the entire local market or other areas. If the centralised server is compromised, the entire network's integrity is called into doubt. Many other authors, such as Miraz and Ali also described their solutions or their work in blockchain technology [39] to synthesise the research on using blockchain and related distributed ledger technologies outside of the cryptocurrency sector and derive the right conclusions. The purpose of Ref. [40] is to present a comprehensive literature assessment of 69 high-quality, peer-reviewed papers that capture the motivations and challenges to blockchain adoption, applications, and implementation phases within FSCs. Alt [41] summarised the situation of Zume Pizza, a California start-up that was the first to use robots to bake pizza.

On ten parameters, the proposed system is compared to the previously discussed current systems. These criteria are explained briefly below:

- *Protection against a single point failure:* Ability to endure a network failure if a single/main node fails.
- *Ingredient certification* ability for raw material authenticity checking.
- *Ingredient quality checking* is the ability to check the quality of genuine food in the local market or any other restaurant from all over India.
- *Lot/Batch No./Serial No. to package* ability to check the integrity of the foodstuff material.
- *Details of ingredients on bill* ability to give satisfaction to any customer after taking food from any restaurant.
- *Reliability of operation* signifies a network's ability to perform traditional supply chain activities and operations seamlessly.
- *Involvement of partners* is the degree to which a system encourages participation from relevant parties.
- *Privacy* capability to communicate or deliver material without misleading communication.
- *Transparency:* A system's transparency may be defined as the degree to which outside parties can see its transactions.

Table 3
Performance analysis.

Configuration#	Endorsing node	Ordering node	Committing node	Throughput (blocks/s)
1	1	1	1	10
2	1	2	1	8
3	1	3	1	9
4	2	4	1	5
5	2	4	2	5
6	2	5	2	4
7	2	5	1	4
8	3	1	2	8
9	3	1	1	9
10	3	1	2	7
11	3	2	1	6
12	3	2	2	6
13	3	3	1	6
14	3	3	2	5
15	3	4	1	5

Fig. 9. System configuration versus throughput.

Fig. 10. Ordering node vs. throughput.

- *Security* capability of the system is to protect against unwanted access.
- *Immutability* is a property to which data must not be changed.

7. Challenges and potential solutions

When considering the implementation of blockchain technology in the context of food security, several challenges related to scalability, compatibility issues, and high setup costs need to be addressed. The following is a discussion of these challenges and potential solutions.

(a) Uncertainty of system scalability

Scalability is a significant concern when implementing blockchain technology, especially in systems where large volumes of data transactions occur, such as in food supply chains. As the number of transactions increases, the blockchain network can become slow and inefficient, leading to delays and increased costs.

Solution: Implement sharding techniques where the blockchain is divided into smaller, more manageable parts. Each shard processes its transactions, allowing the system to handle a higher transaction throughput.

Off-chain transactions: Move some transactions off the main blockchain. Sidechains or off-chain solutions can be utilised for less critical transactions to reduce the load on the main blockchain.

(b) Compatibility issues with other systems

Integrating blockchain technology with existing systems, especially in complex supply chain networks, can be challenging due to compatibility issues. Legacy systems might not communicate effectively with blockchain platforms, leading to data discrepancies and operational inefficiencies.

Solution: Develop APIs and middleware solutions that act as intermediaries between the blockchain network and existing systems. These tools facilitate seamless data exchange and communication.

Fig. 11. Committing node vs. throughput.

Fig. 12. Endorsing node vs. throughput.

Standards and interoperability: Establish industry standards for data formats and communication protocols to ensure compatibility between different systems within the supply chain.

(c) High setup costs

Implementing blockchain technology involves substantial initial setup costs, including infrastructure, development, and training. For organisations, especially in the food industry, these costs can be a significant barrier to adoption.

Solution: Consider using cloud-based blockchain platforms. Cloud solutions can reduce infrastructure costs and offer scalable options, allowing businesses to pay for the resources they use.

Collaborative initiatives: Participate in collaborative initiatives and consortia where multiple organisations share the costs of developing and maintaining blockchain infrastructure. Shared resources can significantly reduce individual setup costs.

In summary, addressing the challenges of scalability, compatibility,

high setup costs, regulatory concerns, and awareness is crucial when applying blockchain technology to food security blockchains. By employing innovative solutions and collaborating with industry partners, organisations can overcome these challenges and harness the full potential of blockchain to enhance food security measures.

8. Implications of work

The proposed approach has numerous ramifications, each of which is explored in depth using an example.

- 1) When a restaurant owner purchases raw materials from a retailer and delivers them to the inventory department of the restaurant, they enter the details into the database according to the labels. Then, they provide all the items to the cook or chef for cooking. However, if the chef or cook adulterates the ingredients while preparing the food, or if they reuse or sell the leftover materials, it degrades the quality of the food. However, if they use a blockchain-based application, this

Table 4
Existing system vs. the proposed system.

Assessment parameter	Conventional systems	dos Santos et al. [21]	Cocco et al. [36]	Radain et al. [35]	Proposed system
Protection against single point failure	×	×	✓	×	✓
Ingredient certification	×	✓	✓	×	✓
Ingredient quality checking	×	✓	×	✓	✓
Lot/Batch No./ Serial No. to package	×	×	×	×	✓
Details of ingredients on bill	×	×	×	×	✓
Reliability of operation	×	×	×	×	✓
Involvement of partner	×	×	×	×	✓
Privacy	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
Transparency	×	×	×	×	✓
Security	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
Immutability	×	✓	✓	×	✓

will not be possible because if the QR code-enabled material is resold, it can be easily traced. It will have an already-sold tag associated with it.

- 2) A blockchain-based application can help food inspection agencies conduct frequent restaurant inspections and verify the quality of food and materials. Surprise inspections are highly beneficial when complaints occur. It would be nearly difficult for anyone to sell or reuse any remaining materials in the restaurant due to the multiple documented handovers in the logistics of the food supply chain. As a result, tracing back to the original source and identifying the parties responsible becomes relatively simple.
- 3) Any expired ingredient can be easily tracked, and no supply chain stakeholder can change its expiration date. Anyone attempting to do so will be immediately identifiable and tracked.
- 4) Today, most health issues arise due to poor food quality. Whenever someone visits a restaurant, they expect to have a good meal without experiencing any adverse effects on their health. When it comes to bill payments, it is important to ensure that the transaction is a genuine transaction, meaning that the food we consume aligns with the proper ingredients and is served in the correct quantity, thereby minimising any potential health issues. Therefore, the proposed blockchain-based application will help address these types of issues.

9. Conclusions

The present article starts by providing an overview of the complexities and obstacles encountered in contemporary mainstream food traceability systems. This study introduces a novel blockchain-based system that aims to guarantee the integrity and genuineness of food services throughout the entirety of the food supply chain network. A significant number of individuals are now afflicted or succumb to illness due to the consumption of food that is either inauthentic or polluted. Traceability and the food supply chain are critical components for guaranteeing food safety. Customers would be able to check the authenticity of cooked food or food supplies using the proposed method. The blockchain-based application is intended to construct a decentralised network with the help of 15 nodes. The system's performance was evaluated using several network topologies, with throughput serving as the primary performance parameter. The proposed system was

determined to possess a high computational burden since the duration needed to execute a transaction increases in proportion to the quantity of nodes involved. Conversely, increasing the number of participating nodes enhances the accessibility of nodes in achieving agreement, a critical aspect in ensuring the system's resistance to tampering. Although the system may be conveniently accessed via mobile applications for instantaneous QR code scanning, it is incapable of independently eliminating the consumption of unauthorised or counterfeit food or substances. Foodborne diseases remain a significant public health concern globally, despite advancements in food science and safety. The society supports the proposed mechanism because it addresses health concerns. Furthermore, blockchain technology with ledger-based record-keeping mechanisms is also being used in other domains, such as courier management, to optimise food-tracking systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sachin Yele: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Ratnesh Litoriya:** Conceptualization, All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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